

Impact of HRM Practices on Job Satisfaction, Evidence from Private Universities of Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: Human Resource Management includes conducting job analyses, planning personnel needs, recruiting the right people for the right job at right time, orienting and training them. This study is related to the impact of the HRM practices on the employee job satisfaction. In the private sector universities, employees are not satisfied with their jobs even in the presence of the HRM practices. For this study simple random sampling is used and the limitations of our study are the private sector universities. A questionnaire has been used to collect primary data based on structured questions. Results shows that the HRM practices (Recruitment and Selection, Compensation and Pay Package, Training and Development, Rewards and Motivation) have more significant effects on employees' job satisfaction in comparison of Working Environment. Further research may be done to achieve high level of job satisfaction.

Keywords: HRM, Recruitment, Selection, Environment, Training, Development, Compensation, Pay Package, Private Universities

Introduction

Every organization needs the best performance from their employees towards the achievements of the organizational goals through demonstration of the tasks by innovatively and effectively in this modern a competitive era of business (Katz, 1964). To achieve this goal, most of the organizations invest their capital in the human resource and practicing the human resource practices in their respective organizations like recruitment and selection, provide healthy working environment, trained their employees in the new working techniques and pay the handsome compensation and pay packages, appraisal systems and finally award the financial or non-financial reward which ultimately motivate their employees to achieve their organizational goals (Dessler G. , 2009).

Previous researchers advocated that HRM practices are very much integrated with the job satisfaction of the employees (Koch & McGrath, 1996; Huselid, 1995). These HRM practices positively affect the employee's commitment and effectiveness of organizations (Yeung & Berman, 1997).

Education sector plays a vital role in the process of development of any country. Nowadays investors learn the importance of the education and get the idea that the education is a very lucrative market in business sector. In Pakistan, education sector is a very profitable business nowadays. In Pakistan, total 175 universities are working from which 100 universities are operating their functions under the auspices of the federal and provincial (Punjab, Sindh, KPK, Balochistan and Gilgit Baltistan) governments and 75 universities are functioning under the umbrella of the private sector (HEC, 2017).

Job Satisfaction of employees in the universities attracts academic scholars, social scientist, and many more brilliant scholars from different fields. Past studies emphasized that the quality of education cannot be provided to the students without satisfied employees of the universities. This is the reason which is being adopted by the most of the universities across the globe to provide the healthy, conducive, peaceful working environment along-with financial benefits of the employees of the universities in order to get more satisfaction in their jobs (Hyder & Batool, 2013).

According to the previous researches employees working in private sector universities are less satisfied with their jobs as compared to the public sector universities (Hyder & Batool, 2013). The main purpose of this research is to identify the reason of the unsatisfied employees towards their jobs in the private sector universities in Pakistan. Most of the researches were conducted on the job satisfaction of the universities employees in Pakistan on public sector universities. This research provides the comprehensive reasons why the employees of the private sector universities are less satisfied from their jobs.

Research Objective

To determine the effects of HRM practices on Job Satisfaction among the employees of private universities in the Pakistan

1. To examine the impact of Recruitment and Selection on Job Satisfaction.
2. To examine the impact of Working Environment on Job Satisfaction
3. To examine the impact of Compensation and Pay Package on Job Satisfaction.

4. To examine the impact of Training and Development on Job Satisfaction.
5. To examine the impact of Rewards and Motivation on Job Satisfaction.

Literature Review

Recruitment & Selection

Recruitment & selection contains the two major interrelated variables. First, recruitment which means to create a set of suitable incumbent which are most suitable for the job in an organization and the selection is a transformational process of the suitable individuals from the recruitment process for doing work under the policies and objectives of the management of the organization (Bratton & Gold, 2012). Recruitment is the process to fill completely the vacant positions in organizations by sufficient characteristics in the applicants which ultimately meets the requirement and expectation of the organization (Shen & Edwards, 2004). According to this concept, HR Manager has an indispensable role to hire the suitable incumbents which have required capabilities and competencies which organizations require for the advertised positions (Marques, 2007). R & S plays a vital role in the success of the organizations and prime importance towards the job satisfaction for obtaining the high quality professionals but it is not an easy task for the organizations to hire the most suitable incumbents (Gopinath & Shibu, 2014).

Working Environment

Supportive and attracting working environment attracts the employees to remain in their professions and encourages them to be the part of the workforce of the organization and work effectively (Oswald, 2012). Healthy working environmental condition empowers the employees to work effectively in the organization and create an environment in which employees' best use of their knowledge, competences, skills and the resources available to get the high performance in the services (Leshabari, Muhondwa, Mwangu, & Mbembati, 2008).

Workplace environment are two types named behavioral and physical (Stallworth & Kleiner, 1996). Haynes (2008) revealed that physical environment consists of two major categories, first is office layout which depends on the open plane vs virtual offices and office comfort which compare the office environment with work processes and the behavioral environment majorly describe the two vital categories like interaction with peers and distraction. Improvements in the physical facilities may results 5-10 percent productivity increase and finally performance incensement. (Barry, 2008). Scott (2000) investigated that working environment conditions are closely associated with job satisfaction.

Compensation and Pay Package

Compensation and pay package plays a vital role in the life of an employee working life. Awareness about the pay package satisfies more employees and pay more attention towards the satisfaction on the workplace rather than the negative awareness creates negative affectivity on the satisfaction on the workplace. Organ (1994) revealed that positive and negative awareness about the salary plays a vital role towards job satisfaction. Low level of salary satisfaction affects the job performance. In the modern era, the organizations introduce the integrated salary packages to enhance the performance level of the employees such as incentives in groups and profits distribution schemes (Solomon, 1986). Apparent justice in the distribution of incentives polices causes the pleasure in the employees. Integrated distribution of the compensation results in uplifting the employees towards their jobs (Fong, Shaffer, & Centre, 2001). Flaherty and Pappas (2002) claimed that more turnover and lower job satisfaction saw in the employees who paid a fixed pay package rather than the salespeople with lower turnover and high level of satisfaction in the organizations. A well-established relationship was seen in the salary level and job satisfaction without any complexity (Herzberg, Mausner, Peterson, & Capwell, 1957). Previous researches revealed that there is positive relationship between compensation and pay package with job satisfaction, higher the pay package higher the job satisfaction and lower the pay package lower the job satisfaction (Beutell, Nicholas, Wittig-Berman, & Ursula, 1999; Igalens & Roussel, 1998).

Training & Development

Training is a modification of an official and precise behavior by taking that relate to the concept of after the impact of education and improve the experience of arranging share (Armstrong, A Handbook of Human Resource Practice, 2001). Training on the job quota for the cause compelling alternative may be working off referred to the appropriate training may be needed for different needs. A close examination directed towards Koch and McGrath (1996) showed that organizations that captivate a deliberate training for their labour force need the help less dislike should be feted on those paid that is only the tip of the profitable iceberg workforce. It found Armstrong (2001) show that the effects of the training commitment and loyalty, User information and respect-based organization of the same. Similarly, Bartel (1994) found that

the program supports the training staff and the staff determination to build confidence and improve services. In policies and training and development allows public employees to receive more excellent competencies would be properly performing their duties proficiently and effectively.

Reward and Motivation

Reward is a vital element in any organization to build and sustain the employees' commitment towards organization and setting up the high performance standards (Wang, 2004). Reward provides the exchange services between employer and its employees (Luthans & Sommers, 2005; Edwards, Cable, Williamson, Lambert, & Shipp, 2006). Edwards, et al. (2006) and Zaini, et al. (2009) claimed that rewards depending on the job specification and job description and uphold the equity between the employees in the organization as well as in the competitive market. Rewards can be classified into two categories (i) intrinsic rewards (energy, feelings of passion, autonomy and enthusiasm) and (ii) extrinsic rewards (co-worker relationship, pay and security) (Abdullah, 1994). Intrinsic motivation rises due to the intrinsic rewards and extrinsic motivation signifies due to the extrinsic rewards (Bjorkman & Budhwar, 2007).

Motivation got central significance in the process of learning in the organizations (Amabile, Hill, Hennessey, & Tighe, 1994). Motivation is an internal element of the human and it can also be divided into two groups (i) intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation (McShane & Glinow, 2008). Luthans (2005) suggested that "Psychological processes that origin the stimulation, direction, and persistence of behaviour".

Job satisfaction can be probed through the motivation and the setting of environment and psychological circumstances (Milne, 2007). JS increases in the employees who received more rewards of both categories from their firms (Kiviniemi et al., 2002). High salary and promotion are the key factors for motivation and ultimately for JS (Lepak & Snell, 1999). In the current vivacious era of business the more motivation in the employees show more job performance and deliver their services a synergy for the fulfillment of the goals of organizations, higher proficiency, business strategies, performance and growth which ultimately resulted more job satisfaction (Jehanzeb, Rasheed, Rasheed, & Aamir, 2012).

Job Satisfaction

Vroom (1964) defined the Job Satisfaction as "it is an orientation of emotions that employees possess towards role they are performing at the work place". JS is an integrated package of physiological, psychological and environmental working conditions which boost up the employees to admit that whether he is happy or satisfied with his job and working environment (Hoppok & Spielgler, 1938). If employees do not satisfy with their jobs which are assigned by the higher management, they will not assure about the factors like basic rights, unsafe working conditions, non-cooperation by the co-workers and getting less respect by their supervisor and ultimately they are not took on board in the decision making process which is ultimately resulting the separation from the organization in which they are working (Clark, 1997).

JS plays a vital role in the life of employees working in the organizations in the sense of performance, motivation, work efficiency and last but not the least mental health (Potkany & Giertl, 2013). The researchers explained the human problem and also include in the labour process and create the relationship to their work. Slovakian researchers paid a great attention to JS in the 60s and 80s of twentieth century (Dubayova, 1976). JS is the emotional and favorable condition which can get in the form of results from work evaluation and experience of work (Výrost, 1998). To identify the job satisfaction on working places are the work attitudes and these help in the evaluation of subjects, people, events and phenomena play a vital role in the human personality.

Job satisfaction of employees can be considered as one of the important factors for improving the organizational performance. The hotels of Malaysia similar to the other countries attempt to increase employee job satisfaction. In this regard, (HRM) human resource management practices can have a critical role. This is consistent with theory of resource based view (RBV). According to RBV, companies can use their own human resource in order to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. Among different HRM practices, this study focused on training, staffing; performance appraisal and also reward system (Farahbod, Arzi, 2014).

In current era of highly volatile business environment organizations are facing emerging challenges in form of acquisition and optimization of human resource. Being valuable and scarce capabilities, human resources are considered as a source of sustainable competitive advantage. The success of an organization depends upon several factors but the most crucial factor that affects the organization performance is its employee. Human resources play an integral role in achieving an innovative and high-quality product/ service (Jeet, Sayeeduzzafar, 2014).

Conceptual Framework

Methodology

This study is descriptive and cross-sectional in nature. Convenient sampling and survey technique are used to collect data from the employees working in the private universities of Pakistan. A survey strategy is used to examine and analyze the impact HRM practices on employee job satisfaction of private sector universities. For this study leading Private Sector University are taken as population. There is 2250 total number of employees in the university. By using the sampling formula 329 employees will be the sample. (n = sample size, N = Population and e = Margin of errors) $n = N / 1 + N \times e^2$.

$$= 2250 / 1 + 2250 \times 0.05^2$$

$$= 2250 / 1 + 2250 \times 0.0025$$

$$= 2250 / 6.25 \quad n = 329$$

Due to the busy schedule we are not able to collect the data from 329 people consequently we collected the data from 290 people. The sample units include Faculty Members, Supporting Staff and Admin Staff of the private universities situated in Lahore, Pakistan. For obtaining information two stage sampling is used. In this technique first, we select randomly three departments (Mechanical Engineering, Management Sciences and Medical Department. Secondly, we equally distributed the respondent in three categories (Teaching, Teaching Supporting and Admin Staff). A structured questionnaire is developed. It has two parts: first is based general information and the second part is related to the HRM practices. For the study 290 respondents were contacted for getting the information regarding Human Resource Management practices in the university. Due to the busy schedule of the departments 256 respondents were respond which is 88.28% of the total contacted respondents.

Model Specification

For analyzing the impact of Human Resource Management on job satisfaction in private sector universities the linear regression model is used by using SPSS. The regression model is depicted as:-

$$JS = \alpha + \beta(RS) + \beta(WE) + \beta(CP) + \beta(TD) + \beta(RM) + e$$

Dependent & Independent Variables

Job Satisfaction (JS) of the universities' employees is dependent variable and Recruitment and Selection (RS), Working Environment (WE), Compensation and Pay Package (CP), Training and Development (TD) and Reward and Motivation (RM) are the independent variables in the regression model.

Hypothesis

For examine the impact of HRM practices on Job Satisfaction the following hypothesis are framed.

1. Recruitment and Selection significantly associated with Job Satisfaction.
2. Working Environment significantly associated with Job Satisfaction
3. Compensation and Pay Package significantly associated with Job Satisfaction.
4. Training and Development significantly associated with Job Satisfaction.
5. Rewards and Motivation significantly associated with Job Satisfaction.

Reliability Test

We apply the test of reliability of the scales which are very much important before apply the regular statistical tests. By applying this test we found the reliability of the scale generates consistent results if the measurement were made repeatedly. This is done by the defining the association in between the scores obtained from the different scales. If association is high, the scales produces consistent results, thus it is reliable. For this purpose Cronbach's Alpha technique is widely used. Its value varies in between 0 to 1. But the acceptable value is required to be more than 0.6 which determines the reliability of the scales (Cronbach, 1951). Our questionnaire reliability is about 0.825 which is very much close to 1. It's mean that the instrument which we are using for this study is strongly reliable. The values of Cronbach's Alpha scale are as follows:-

Table – 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.825	19

Analysis

The analysis is divided into two parts. First one is demographic information (designation, profession, age, experience) and second one is analytical statistics related to the independent and dependent variables (Recruitment & Selection, Working Environment, Compensation & Pay Package, Training & Development and Reward and Motivation). In first part of the analysis we took mean of the variables. Firstly, a request form made to request the respondent for filling the questionnaire by sparing ten (10) minutes from their busy schedules. The total 290 questionnaires was floated with a set of a ball point and white paper in the different in the Engineering, Social Sciences and Medical Sciences faculties of private universities located in the Lahore, Pakistan. Out of 290 structured questionnaires 256 questionnaires was find correct and a. The corrected questionnaires' data was entered in the SPSS for data analysis. While apply descriptive statistics in the SPSS version 20. The following numbers obtained which are mentioned in the table no. 2

Table – 2: Descriptive Statistics

Items	Description	Frequency	%age
Age	20-30	135	52.5%
	31-40	62	24.1%
	41-50	46	17.9%
	Above 50	13	5.1%
Gender	Male	152	59.1%
	Female	104	40.5%
Education	Diploma	67	26.1%
	Graduate	105	40.9%
	Postgraduate	84	32.7%
Designation	Admin Staff	60	23.3%
	Teaching Staff	170	66.1%
	Supporting Staff	26	10.1%
Field of Work	Engineering	103	40.1%
	Social Sciences	84	32.7%
	Medical Sciences	69	26.8%

According to the table – 2, out of 256 respondents 135 (52.5%), 62 (24.1%), 46 (17.9%) and 13 (5.1%) are lying in the age group of 20-30, 31-50, 41-50 and above 50 years respectively. 152 (59.1%) are male and 104 (40.5%) are female respondents. According to the education there are three categories like diploma holders are 67 (26.1%), graduate degree holders are 105 (40.9%) and 84 (32.7%) are having postgraduate degree which is the highest percentage among the employees according to the education. Admin staff of the universities having strength according to our survey is 60 (23.3%), Teaching Staff 170(66.1%) and supporting staff are in the strength of 26 (10.1%). Field of the work are categorizes into three groups Engineering 103 (40.1%), social Sciences 84 (32.7%) and medical sciences 69 (26.8%).

Correlation Test

Table – 3: Pearson Coefficients Correlation

	Job Satisfaction	Recruitment & Selection	Training & Development	Compensation & Pay Package	Working Environment	Reward & Motivation
Job Satisfaction	1					
Recruitment & Selection	.212	1				
Training & Development	.242	.111	1			
Compensation & Pay Package	.575**	.218	-.218	1		
Working Environment	.408**	.272	-.272	.802**	1	
Reward & Motivation	.364**	-.389	-.167	-.145	-.068	1

Table – 3 show the results of correlation coefficient and suggested that all the relationships among the variables are positive and highly significant. The values of the correlation shows that all the hypothesis (H1, H2, H3, H4, H5) can be

accepted to affirm that the HRM practices are positively associated with the job b satisfaction of the employees working in the private sector universities in the Pakistan.

To get deep understanding the correlation of the variable from the table – 3, compensation and pay package is strongly associated with the job satisfaction with the value of 0.575 and $P < .01$. It means that if management of the universities put more efforts on these practices of HRM to pay healthy compensation and pay package to the employees then they get more satisfaction from the employees’ side. Therefore, the 3rd hypothesis of the study which is compensation and pay package significantly associated with job satisfaction is accepted and there is a strongly relationship between CPP and JS. Moreover, working environment has the second highest value in the table towards JS which is 0.408 with $P < .01$. According to this value our 4th hypothesis is also accepted that the higher management of the private universities in Pakistan delivers more on this practice of HRM in order to get more satisfied employees in their universities due the availability of the highly competitive marketplace and also due to the increasing rates of unemployment in Pakistan.

Table – 3 claimed that the reward and motivation has the greater extent with JS of the employees are engaged in with the private universities and the value of the Pearson correlation is 0.364 with $P < .01$. Hypothesis No. 5 is accepted which constitutes a point of view that managers of the private universities in Pakistan should practice the power culture in their universities to get more satisfaction among the employees.

Training and development revealed more significant value (.242, $P < .01$) in the correlation table with JS which suggested that second hypothesis is accepted. This also shows that the universities do this HRM practice in their universities and get their employees up-to-date with the latest trainings and develop them with latest tools of their field in to get more satisfy them. It is due to the rapid development in the field of technology.

However, recruitment and selection is relatively less associated but has positive correlation with JS as indicated by the table – 3. The value of the recruitment and selection is 0.212 and P-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.01. This tells the management that if they put less focus on this variable and more on the others, the JS relatively high in the employees. A fair process of recruitment and selection posit the higher degree of JS in the employees.

Regression analysis

Table – 4: Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.871	.794	.775	.445

Table – 5: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	51.245	6	8.262	34.106	.000 ^b
Residual	10.255	44	.236		
Total	61.500	50			

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Recruitment and Selection, Working Environment Compensation and Pay Package, Training and Development, Reward and Motivation

Table – 6: coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-14.876	1.232		-11.311	.000
Recruitment & Selection	.505	.149	.277	3.229	.002
Working Environment	-.379	.316	-.170	-1.221	.231
Compensation & Pay Package	2.049	.281	.851	7.301	.000
Training & Development	.861	.169	.473	5.043	.000
Reward & Motivation	1.188	.150	.643	8.188	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

To do deep analysis and interpret the variables' values obtained during the data analysis, a multiple regression analysis is undertaken by using SPSS in order to predict the job satisfaction as dependent variable by HRM practices as independent variables. Recruitment and Selection, Working Environment, Compensation and Pay Package, Training and Development and Reward and Motivation are the independent variables and Job Satisfaction is the dependent variable revealed by the table-4 and table-5.

The independent variables are significantly related with JS and jointly predict the JS. The F value is equal to 34.106, $R^2 = .794$ and $P < 0.01$. It means that 79.4% job satisfaction of the employees working in the private sector universities in Pakistan counted by the independent variables used in the regression model. However, we confidently said according to the finds of the regression model that HRM practices are very much essential to predict the JS of the employees of the private sector universities in Pakistan.

Table – 6 revealed that R & S ($\beta = .505$, $t = 3.229$, $P < 0.01$), CPP ($\beta = 2.049$, $t = 7.301$, $P < 0.01$), T & D ($\beta = .861$, $t = 5.043$, $P < 0.01$) and R & M ($\beta = 1.188$, $t = 8.188$, $P < 0.01$) are positively related with the JS and having significant value less than 0.01 and WE ($\beta = -.379$, $t = -1.221$, $P > 0.01$) found insignificant and having negative relationship with JS of the employees of the private sector universities in Pakistan.

Limitation and Future Direction

This study has the limitation of variable and pure related to the private sector universities in Pakistan. Due to shortage of the time, private universities (The University of Lahore, University of Central Punjab, University of Management & Technology, Superior University, NCBA & E, Beconhouse National University, Minhaj University, Riphah International University, etc.) were taken as they population which are situated in Lahore. Faculties are also limited by the researchers.

Future researchers can add more variables in the model and they can also conduct longitudinal research in some other industries like automobile, information technology, consumer products, plantation, public sector universities, etc. as well.

Conclusion

The present study is an attempt to examine and analyze the impact of Human Resource Management practices on job satisfaction of private sector university employees in Pakistan. In the present study, the estimated regression model identified that the HRM practices like Recruitment & Selection, Compensation & Pay Package, Training & Development and Reward & Motivation have a significant impact on job satisfaction but Working Environment is relatively less significant to the job satisfaction of the employees in private universities in Pakistan. Management of the private sector universities in Pakistan may put more efforts to implement the HRM practices in their universities in order to get higher Job Satisfaction among the employees and ultimately beneficial for universities.

The study recommends that private universities have to build new systems to improve Human Resource Management practices. Human Resource Management practices like Training, Performance Appraisal, Team Work and Compensation may be improved in order to achieve high level of job satisfaction.

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